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From expansion to overshoot: Policy risks in managing offshore fisheries expansion

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Abstract

Fishing grounds frequently expand as overfishing of the nearshore promotes policies to increase access and economic incentives to target offshore resources. Subsidies for boats, gear, and fuel have been introduced to shift effort offshore and compensate for declining catches. Therefore, I tested the hypothesis that fishing area expansion would increase the use of offshore-oriented gears and benthic catch losses would be compensated by increased pelagics. To evaluate these increased access strategies, I analyzed 23 years of effort, gear use, and catch data from 13 nearshore fisheries in Kenya, nine of which expanded spatially while four remained stable. Initially, expansion correlated with higher fishing effort and increased use of beach seines and ring nets. Beach seine use declined in the non-expanding and rose in the expanding fisheries, despite being made illegal 6 years after catch measurements began. Thereafter, effort and catch rates declined rapidly below the initial and non-expanding fisheries values. Pelagic catches rose cyclically after the decline but for 15 years failed to fully offset benthic losses. Although nearshore fishable biomass and production recovered modestly as fisher numbers fell, capture consistently exceeded local ecological production. Policies promoting offshore fishing access should consider that pelagic yields are potentially low and episodic and may not reliably replace the higher and more stable benthic production. To achieve nearshore fish

recovery, enhanced resource protection coincident with offshore access will be required.

Keywords: coral reef fish production, ecological overshoot, fisheries gear policies, fisheries recovery, pelagic offshore fishing, subsidies

1. Introduction

Global fisheries often follow a trajectory of spatial expansion and ecological homogenization as nearshore, high-trophic-level resources become overexploited (Pauly et al. 2002; Thurston et al. 2010, 2018). This shift typically replaces diverse nearshore species with benthic herbivores, omnivores, and pelagic fishes (Houk et al. 2018; Morais and Bellwood 2019; McClanahan et al. 2025). However, offshore expansion can marginalize artisanal fishers lacking the capital to access distant resources (Nolan 2019; Said and MacMillan 2020). Consequently, many tropical nearshore fisheries remain dominated by low-income fishers targeting suboptimal catches (Giron-Nava et al. 2021; McClanahan et al. 2023; Teh et al. 2024). While some argue poverty stems from limited access (Basurto et al. 2025), others report access restrictions reduce poverty (McClanahan 2001; Ngoc et al. 2026). Moreover, decisions to enter or exit fisheries often hinge on expected earnings relative to fishers' wealth and rising costs of living rather than financial capital and legal access restrictions (Daw et al. 2012; Dao et al. 2023; McClanahan and Kosgei 2025; McClanahan 2026).

To address offshore access barriers, governments frequently subsidize boats, gear, and fuel (Skerritt et al. 2021), aiming to reduce nearshore pressure and promote stock recovery. Yet, the ecological and socioeconomic outcomes of such subsidies are rarely evaluated over the long term (McClanahan and Kosgei 2019). These policies assume sufficient offshore stocks and sustained compensatory production, as well as a nearshore recovery following a meaningful decline in nearshore effort—assumptions that remain largely untested (Binch et al. 2025). Cultural and economic factors further influence fishers' willingness to adopt riskier offshore practices and whether benefits offset added costs (Froese et al. 2025).

Understanding benthic and pelagic production and capture dynamics is critical for assessing whether offshore yields can compensate or replace nearshore losses (Birkeland 2017). However, long-term quantitative data are scarce. This study

addresses these gaps by analyzing 23 years of catch and gear-use data from Kenya's fringing reef during a period of spatial and subsidy expansion. Management responses included gear restrictions, community-based governance through Beach Management Units (BMUs), and subsidies for offshore access, all occurring amid rapid population growth and governance decentralization (McClanahan 2026).

We hypothesized that fishing area expansion would increase the use of offshore-oriented gears (handlines and various nets). In nearshore habitats, continued competition would favor smaller-meshed nets, smaller-hooked handlines, and spearguns over traps (McClanahan and Mangi 2004; Ontomwa et al. 2019). Offshore trends were expected to compensate for lost benthic catch but also to vary with local coastal geography, economics, regulatory enforcement, and compliance (Supplementary Table S1). To test these predictions, I monitored 13 coral reef fisheries—nine expanding and four stable or contracting—to evaluate changes in effort, gear composition, and catch dynamics under a governance focused on expanding area and fishing subsidies (Njiru et al. 2021).

1.1 Fisheries Context

Key decision-makers in Kenya's fisheries include county fisheries officers, park service staff, and local Beach Management Unit (BMU) leaders established under governance reforms following the 2013 constitutional changes. Coastal fishing grounds exhibit typical signs of overfishing, gear competition, and declining effort as fishers exit the sector even when given gear and boat subsidies (McClanahan and Azali 2020; McClanahan and Kosgei 2019). This study draws on a long-term monitoring partnership between the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS) and the Kenyan Fisheries Department aimed at assessing coral reef fisheries' production capacity, informing management decisions, reducing poverty, and conserving biodiversity. The project measured fish biomass estimated production and maximum sustainable

yields, and promoted stock recovery through education, stakeholder agreements, and management interventions.

1.2 Fisheries Regulations

Kenya's Fisheries Management and Development Act (2016) and local BMU bylaws proposed to regulate gear use, banning beach seines, seine nets with mesh sizes under 45 mm, explosives, poisons, electric shockers, and unauthorized fish aggregating devices (Table S1). Rules restricting the size and type of fishing boats by distance from shore were initiated by national fisheries regulations after the presented time series. Therefore, there was no regulations and effort to restrict movements offshore and fishing by vessel size and types during this study period. Despite rules, enforcement was inconsistent, and data collection included all landed gears. In WCS data collection, nets are grouped into four main categories—beach seines, gill nets, ring nets, and small reef nets—out of approximately 14 net types in use. Beach seines and ring nets are not used universally but remained active in some locations through local agreements (Okemwa et al. 2025). National and county governments periodically subsidize fishers with motorized boats and gill nets exceeding 45 mm mesh size.

2. Methods

2.1 Study Sites

Kenya's fringing reef spans approximately 200 km of coastline, forming a lagoon that extends 0.5–2 km offshore (Fig. 1). Beyond the reef edge, the seabed transitions to sand and rubble at depths of ~20 m, where low sunlight limits the growth of seagrass and benthic algae. Detritus accumulation supports a low-biomass detrital ecosystem, while pelagic planktivores and deep-water detritivores species dominate offshore habitats. Consequently, benthic productivity declines with depth, and catches shift toward pelagic taxa as fishing moves offshore. Lagoon environments provide

sheltered conditions, enabling low-cost fishing with small wooden boats, foot, or fins in shallow waters (<20 m) (Table S2). Offshore effort is poorly documented, with one study reporting increased catches beyond the reef during the calm northeast monsoon (November–April) (Thoya and Daw 2019). However, Kaunda-Arara et al. (2016) reported declines and changes in catch composition in offshore deep-water trawl catches over a >30 years interval at >50-m depths. National fisheries data have been analyzed from the 1950s to 2014 and found to have fisheries-dependent maximum sustained yield (MSY) of ~10 tons/km²/y at ~12 fishers/km²/y (Tuda and Wolf 2015).

2.2 Mapping Fishing Grounds

Fish landing sites are located on beaches where catches are weighed and sold. The study sites are a simple linear fringing reef system where it is easy to measure area as the distance from the low tide to the furthest offshore distance where fishing occurs. Fishing area estimates were derived for 13 landing sites initially in 1995 and repeated in 2018. Boundaries were defined midway between adjacent sites, and expansion was primarily based on the observed and reported distances traveled beyond the reef edge (Fig. 1). Mapping the fishing areas employed a participatory process involving a participatory GPS-based area delineation, stakeholder validation, which is more fully described elsewhere (McClanahan and Kosgei 2023). The area within delineated boundaries was calculated from GIS software to estimate per area effort and capture rates. Thereafter, annual Beach Management Unit (BMU) meetings were held to review catch trends and inform management. Two communities established small permanent closures (tengefu, <1 km²) to reduce fishing pressure and these areas were removed from fishing area calculations (McClanahan et al. 2016). In one case the lost area (Kuruwitu) was compensated for by fishing further from shore and in another case (Tradewinds), the area of the fishing grounds was reduced. Areas and their changes varied among sites, and these are detailed in the results.

2.3 Field Methods

2.3.1 Stock Biomass Estimates

Fishable biomass (fish with >10 cm body lengths) was largely assessed annually or semi-annually during the calm northeast monsoon season along the full reef profile using 500 m² belt transects offshore from landing sites at 1 to 20 meters depth between 1987 and 2022 (McClanahan et al. 2015). The weight of the fish was established by converting the mid-point of the length bin (10 cm intervals) to weights using local length-weight calculations taken at the family level from local landing sites. This weight was multiplied by the number of individuals in this family bin and summed for all length bins to obtain total fishable biomass. Biomass typically comprised ~50% target species (snappers, grunts, rabbitfish, parrotfish, large surgeonfish) and ~50% non-target taxa (wrasses, small surgeonfish, and other non-commercial reef species). Surveys covered shallow lagoons less than a few meters depth at low tides to deeper reef edges extending to sand plains. Habitat changes and limits to safe diving required setting a maximum sampled depth to ~20 meters.

Data from adjacent protected areas (closed for up to 54 years) informed a biomass recovery model estimating ecological recovery rates, production/biomass ratios, and equilibrium biomass (McClanahan and Kosgei 2025). Kenya's fringing reef was estimated to have a biomass at maximum ecological sustainable yield (B_{MSY}) of ~50 tons/km², which predicts an optimal production (MSY) estimate of 25.5 ± 4.1 kg/km²/day (=5.6 tons/km²/y) for 220 fishing days annually. These transects sampled the same taxa recorded at landing sites, enabling comparisons between biomass, productivity, and capture rates.

2.3.2 Fish Catch Sampling

Catch data were collected during 18 active lunar fishing days per month, averaging 2.6 ± 0.04 sampling days monthly (28.6 ± 1.2 annually) (Table S6). Observers recorded

fisher numbers, boats, gear types, catch categories, and weights to the nearest 0.1 kg, as previously described (McClanahan and Kosgei 2019). Categories reflected market pricing: goatfish, rabbitfish, scavengers, parrotfish, mixed reef species (often for home consumption), and pelagic species (jacks, tuna, fusiliers, barracuda, anchovies, sardines) (Table S4). Effort, catch, and revenue data were initially recorded manually, later via Kobo Toolbox (<https://eu.kobotoolbox.org/>) and analyzed in R v4.4.2.

2.4 Data Analysis

2.4.1 Stock Biomass Model

Fishable biomass ($n = 239$ site observations collected over time at 47 sites) was modeled using a General Linear Mixed Model (GLMM). Predictors included year (1987–2024), site category (expanding vs. non-expanding), four management types: high compliance, young and low compliance closures, gears restricted, and no gears restricted, and transect depth at neap low tide. Management was classified into two categories: Unfished (high and young and low compliance closures) and fished (gears and no gears restricted). The focus here was on biomass changes in expanding and non-expanding fishing grounds with either no or some gear restrictions (no beach seines and spearguns) and not fisheries closure categories. Fished categories were determined based on direct observation of fishing gears while sampling and communications with knowledgeable stakeholders (McClanahan et al. 2015). Partial plots illustrate biomass trends for both fished reefs categories at 2.75 m (average reef depth) and 15 m (reef edge) depths. The reef edge depth is smaller portion of the total area but represent locations with the highest biomass (McClanahan et al. 2023).

2.4.2 Fish Catch Analyses

Daily catch data were pooled monthly for normalization. Metrics included fishing effort (fishers/km²/day), total catch per area (CPUA, kg/km²/day), and catch per unit effort (CPUE, kg/fisher/day). Daily gear-level metrics pooled to the month included (i)

fishers per gear, (ii) proportion of fishers using each gear (ratio of fishers per gear to total fishers), and (iii) pelagic to total catch ratio (ratio of pelagic catch to total catch). Of 13 fishing grounds, nine expanded and four remained stable (one contracted; see Table S5). Area-based calculations used annualized interpolations based on the initial and final measurements.

Fishers per gear, proportion of fishers per gear, and pelagic to total catch ratio were found to be non-normal after testing for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Differences between expanded and non-expanded sites were evaluated using both exploratory non-parametric tests and generalized linear mixed-effects models with landing site level random intercepts and slopes. The response variables of interest were the gear-level metrics (fishers per gear, proportion of fishers using each gear, pelagic to total catch ratio). Analyses were conducted separately for each gear type.

Initially, the differences between expanded and non-expanded sites in each response variable were tested using Wilcoxon rank-sum test within each gear type.

Subsequently, we fitted generalized linear mixed-effects models (GLMMs) using `glmer` function from `lme4` R package to formally test for differences in temporal trends between area categories while accounting for repeated observations at the same landing sites. The choice of error distribution depended on the response variable where Poisson model was used for fishers per gear, and binomial models were used for proportional responses (proportion of fishers per gear and pelagic-to-total catch ratio).

All models included time and area category as fixed effects, along with their interaction. The general model structure was $\text{response variable} \sim \text{area_category} \times \text{time} + (1 + \text{time} \mid \text{landing_site})$. Ring net data showed a strong imbalance in observations between area categories (Table S3), which prevented reliable estimation of area-category effects. Consequently, the area category variable was omitted, and model specified as: $\text{response variable} \sim \text{time} + (1 + \text{time} \mid \text{landing_site})$. Inferentially,

differences between the area-change categories were evaluated using Wald Z tests within the GLMM modeling framework, which tested whether rates of change over time differed between expanded and non-expanded sites.

Gear-use patterns were assessed via Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using the gear-level variables: fishers per gear, proportion of fishers using each gear, and pelagic to total catch ratio. The gear categories included beach seines, gillnets, handlines, nets, ring nets, spearguns, and traps. Before analysis, the variables were reshaped so that landing site-date combinations formed the rows and gear types formed the columns. This resulted in 3 separate datasets where PCA was applied to each dataset using gear types as variables. PCA was performed with FactoMineR and visualized using factoextra R packages.

Linear regressions were used to illustrate the overall trends over time. Landing site specific slopes and intercepts were derived from the GLMMs results. This was done by combining the population level fixed effect estimates with the corresponding landing site level random effects. These were visualized with linear regression best-fit lines were statistically significant.

3. Results

This section summarizes findings of the differences in fish effort by gear followed by temporal changes in the fisheries, density-dependent patterns in gear use, and lastly the modeled fish production relative to capture rates.

3.1 Fishing Effort by Gear

Gear use varied across landing sites (Fig. 2a,b). Expanding areas showed higher use of beach seines (9.2%) and ring nets (2.2%) compared to non-expanding areas (2.8%, 0.17%) (Table S3). Other gears were similarly distributed: spearguns (~29%), traps (~20%), handlines (~20%), gillnets (~16%), and other nets (~11%).

Daily gear usage rates differed significantly for most gears (Fig. 3). Beach seines and ring nets were more common in expanding areas, though ring nets were infrequent. Gillnets, spearguns, and traps had significantly greater daily use in non-expanding areas, but differences were small (<2 fishers/gear/day). Only traps showed a meaningful effect size with more use in non-expanding areas (Fig. 3b).

3.2 Changes Over Time

3.2.1 Fishing Area

Expanding grounds grew by 71.0% (4.9% annually), from 2.6 to 4.2 km², while non-expanding areas remained ~2.5 km². One site with a community closure shrank by 27%, resulting in a net decline of 3.5% across non-expanding sites (Table S5).

3.2.2 Effort and Catch

Expanding areas had higher initial effort, suggesting expansion was driven by crowding. Effort peaked early, then declined—first in non-expanding areas after 2000, then expanding areas after 2003. Declines in effort were faster in expanding areas (320% calculated by area and 62% as total fishers) than non-expanded areas. Declining effort trends were more predictable in expanding areas ($R^2=0.55$ vs. 0.11) (Fig. 4a). Changes in effort after the peak catches in 2001 for non- and 2003 for expanding areas indicate faster declines in the expanding area. Total and per area declines in the expanding area were -43% and -47% compared to -34% and 20%, respectively.

CPUE changes were weak in non-expanded fishing grounds. Benthic catch declined more strongly in expanding areas ($R^2=0.32$), while pelagic catch rose slightly but did not offset the benthic losses (Fig. 4b,c).

3.2.3 Pelagic Catch

Pelagic catch fluctuated strongly, with larger fluctuating cycles in expanding areas. Ratios of pelagic to total catch increased after effort declined ($R^2=0.31$ in expanding vs. 0.21 in non-expanding), indicating a shift toward offshore pelagic species in both areas (Fig. 4c).

3.2.4 Benthic CPUE

CPUE rose slowly despite rapid effort declines. Benthic CPUE rates increased in all sites, with slower rates in non-expanded (0.02 g/fisher/day) than expanded (0.1 g/fisher/day), but with poor fits in both areas due to high monthly variability ($R^2<0.09$). Moreover, expanding areas saw faster relative increases in CPUE but values started and remained below non-expanding levels (Fig. 4d). While the benthic catch CPUE recovery was ~5 times faster in the expanding than non-expanding area, it never increased to the quantity recorded in the non-expanding areas because of the much lower initial catch (1.6 vs 3.2 kg/fisher/day) and the exceedingly small monthly changes.

3.2.5 Gear Trends

Beach seine use declined in non-expanding but rose and fell intermittently in expanding areas (Tables 1, 2; Fig. S1; Fig. 4e). Gillnets, handlines, and trap use declined in expanding areas; nets increased slightly (ratio 1.07 annually). Handlines were the only gear to increase linearly in non-expanding areas (Tables 1–2). Pelagic catch ratios rose for handlines and spearguns in both area types, while beach seines and trap ratios declined in expanding areas (Table 3).

3.3 Density Dependence

Between-site analyses revealed negative density-dependent trends for gillnets, nets, spearguns, and traps, suggesting density-stabilizing feedback (Fig. 5a,b). Beach seines and ring nets showed no such patterns but had low site replication, while handlines exhibited positive density dependence, indicating attraction around pelagic targets (Fig. 5a,c). Density-dependence is a mechanism for maintaining stability among gears and suggests some of the more traditional benthic gears were stabilized by this negative feedback. In contrast, handlines that can often focus on pelagic fishes showed some positive attraction behavior without negative feedback.

3.4 Modeled Stocks and Capture Rates

GLMM results indicated significant effects of time, expansion status, depth, and fishing status ($R^2=0.65$ and 0.78 with site effects). At the average depth (2.75 m), capture rates (20–40 kg/km²/day) exceeded ecological production (9.23 kg/km²/day), highlighting overexploitation. Deep sites at 15 m showed better alignment between production and capture. Benthic catch loss in expanding areas drove overall declines, partially offset by pelagic catch increases (Fig. 6; Table 4).

4. Discussion

Comparing the expanding and non-expanding fishing area's time series in Kenya shows the evolution of fishing effort, gear, and catch over a time of human population growth and governance changes. During the 23 years of this study, Kenya's national population increased from 27 to 57 million people and the national constitution changed in 2010 to favor local governance spending and management. As fishing areas were only measured twice, there is no evidence to test for either gradual or abrupt changes. Therefore, given the lack of continuous fishing area estimates, it would be speculative to assume a constant annual rate of change estimate over time (e.g., 3.3%). Nevertheless, it is likely the demand for fish increased

proportionally to population growth as reflected by the exponential increase in their landed prices. McClanahan (2026) reported differences in real and nominal landed fish price followed the rising cost of living, where nominal prices increased ~5% and real adjusted-for-inflation prices declined by ~-3% annually. These changes suggest an economic response in pricing that aligned with the human economic need, which often promotes increased offshore access policies and actions.

Despite increased access policies, the minimum per person income and maximum capture production was reached early in the time series between 2001 and 2003, after which effort and yield declined. The decline was largely due to fishing not providing sufficient food and the minimum living wages needed to retain fishers (McClanahan and Kosgei 2025; McClanahan 2026). Consequently, most of the expansion likely occurred during the earlier sampling period and then leveled as the physical limits and economic benefits of expansion were reached. Regardless of the temporal response pattern, expansion temporarily delayed the decline but at the cost of a faster decline after the peak catch. The benthic catch exhibited the greatest loss of capture in the expanded area, which was not fully compensated for by an increase in pelagic catch. Nor did fishers' economic welfare improve with increased access through expansion, subsidies, and poor compliance with gear regulations. Regardless of the enactment of both hypothesized compensatory policy processes, fishers' exiting increased and the welfare of the retained fishers declined.

4.1 Geomorphology and Fishing Ground Expansion

Nearshore reef geomorphology influences the expansion capacity of fishing grounds. Some shallow fringing reefs had restricted access to deeper waters, limiting some area expansion to calm periods, existing breaks in the reef, or during high tides. Larger boats using ring nets were uncommon in non-expanded sites because they require reef gaps for offshore access. Beach seines, in contrast, operate in shallow,

calm waters with sandy or seagrass bottoms and few large corals (Okemwa et al. 2025). These habitat constraints made beach seines and ring nets more prevalent in and around reef breaks, where increased offshore access, higher fisher densities and labor-intensive gear promoted offshore expansion.

Expansion was not measured regularly but it likely increased faster in the early part of this time series up to and shortly after peak catch in 2001-2003. Thereafter, fishing area was expected to reach the limit of the appropriate depths, habitats, and fish resources. Thus, effort declined rapidly as the potential to increase catch was limited and catches per fisher declined near to poverty levels (McClanahan 2026). The rise and fall of catch suggest that expansion could not provide enough fishing grounds to keep pace with the demand, nor to even stabilize the catch. More likely, natural ecological production and net profitability limits were reached. The expansion produced a rise and decline as some fishers moved offshore, as in the case of ring net fishers after 2003. However, fishers began capturing pelagic fish across all fishing areas, not just in the expanding areas. Consequently, it is expected that expansion and the increase in pelagic landings reflected a behavioral response to a local benthic resource production-capture rate imbalance.

4.2 Gear Interactions

Area expansion and increased gear use with small-mesh nets likely promoted inter-gear competitive exclusion of gear that capture larger fish, specifically gillnets, handlines, and traps. Unlike these traditional gears, large seine and ring nets showed little evidence of negative density dependence or self-regulation, which is expected for gears that can expand the area used for fishing. For example, beach seine use increased in expanding areas after 1999 and ring nets after 2003 when the nearshore catch declined. Despite similarities in the core gear used throughout the landing sites, these differences and changes in gears likely influenced the fisheries outcomes as

much as the expansion itself. Specifically, expansion was associated with episodic but increasing use of beach seines.

Some of these episodic changes in beach seines were likely to reflect the interactions with management, as beach seines were declared illegal nationally in Kenya in 2001 (Okemwa et al. 2025). Thereafter, fewer beach seine catches were recorded in non-expanding areas. However, in the expanding areas, their numbers increased gradually after 2001 but rose and fell episodically. A moderate rise in beach seines between 2009 and 2016 corresponded to a peak in published studies focused on beach seines (Okemwa et al. 2025). Many of the negative aspects of beach seines were reported but the usage of beach seines remained in the fishery due to governance challenges and inconsistent enforcement. One common argument for their retention is a lack of political conviction due to the poor's' high dependence on labor intensive gears and their inability to employ other gears and skills. However, low compliance leads to a slow decay in wealth and welfare and an eventual equilibrium of a few resistant fisheries living close to national poverty thresholds (McClanahan 2026).

Several gear exchange programs were instigated between 2003 and 2010 of which some were successful (Okemwa et al. 2025; see her Table 2). However, the data here suggests a resurgence and smaller decline after 2016 until the end of the time series. More detailed knowledge of gear-management interactions would be required to fully understand this variability, as it often depends on the outcomes of local level negotiations between managers and fishers. A regional effort to contain beach seines in Kenya and other African countries has continued, which is associated with the recognition of the long-term loss of benefits and the ecological consequences of their usage (Okemwa et al. 2025).

An early study of the selective capture of fish taxa by gear suggested that beach seines overlap greatly with other common gears (McClanahan and Mangi 2004). Thus, due to their small mesh sizes, beach seines should outcompete other gears. This

prediction is confirmed here by the differences in gear usage between non- and expanding areas. Because this overlap in species capture among gears can lead to competitive exclusion, a policy recommendation has been to reduce beach seines to promote coexistence among gears. Exclusion or a reduction in beach seines was predicted to maintain higher and more sustainable catches, which is supported here by the higher and more stable capture of benthic production in the non-expanding areas. Greater gear diversity is also associated with greater diversity of catch, particularly some of the high value taxa with moderate growth rates, such as found for snappers, grunts, groupers, large surgeonfish, and emperors (McClanahan et al. 2008, 2025).

Beach seine expansion was associated with a decline in the traditional traps, which are among the gears that capture larger individuals, particularly when modified with slotted escape gaps (Gomes et al. 2014; Condy et al. 2015). An experimental study of a gated trap intervention found that gears, such as spearguns, nets, and handlines captured smaller fish that presumably escaped from the gated traps (McClanahan and Kosgei 2018). Consequently, this experimental intervention confirms the competitive mechanisms for the decline in traps in the expanding areas. Gated traps have also been shown to increase the catch's nutrient content, so their loss likely has negative consequences for human health (Galligan et al. 2022).

Ring nets targeted offshore pelagic species but contributed only partially to compensating for benthic catch declines after 2003. Ring nets' high capital and operational costs, coupled with variable catches, raise economic concerns via their profitability and sustainability. Ring nets require considerable costs in terms of boats, fuel, labor, and gear. Moreover, given the high daily variability in catch, establishing if long-term costs are profitable without subsidies is an important economic issue facing their sustainability. Moreover, because spatial variability increases as biomass

declines, it is expected that the high temporal variability in catch will increase as ring net use effort increases (Hseih et al. 2006).

The potential for reciprocal competition for pelagic and benthic fish resources appears to have emerged with area expansion. Ring net fishers were not restricted offshore and often targeted nearshore benthic species during periods of low pelagic yields. Therefore, artisanal fishers complained that ring net fishers often compete with them for nearshore benthic fish. Concurrently, artisanal lines and spearguns increasingly captured more pelagic fish in both non- and expanded areas. Consequently, after this time series, Kenyan regulation in 2022 set a 5 nautical mile minimum distance from shore for ring net usage. While this regulation may be helpful to avoid future competition, there are several challenges to implementing offshore regulations. Specifically, when pelagic fish catch is insufficient to provide ring net fisher sufficient incomes and when support for ensuring monitoring and compliance is low.

4.3 Transition to Pelagic Catches

Pelagic fisheries are generally considered less environmentally damaging than coral reef benthic fisheries. Pelagic catch is attributed to reduced benthic impact on diverse ecosystems, lower bycatch, greater spatial coverage, and improved fuel efficiency among some gears (Birkeland 2017). However, in regions such as southern Kenya, pelagic catches have not fully compensated for declines in benthic fisheries, highlighting the importance of considering production potential and variability when making policy and management decisions.

High variability in pelagic catches is reported across East African fisheries (Sekadende et al. 2020; Kizenga et al. 2021). This variability, driven by complex spatial and temporal dynamics, challenges artisanal fishers' successes when they lack tools to track open-ocean fish schools. Such unpredictability is particularly problematic for

communities reliant on a consistent local supply rather than export markets, as increasing fishing activity can amplify population and catch variability (Hsieh et al. 2006). Schooling pelagic fish populations and attracted fishers may help to increase catch and fishing efficiency to provide high yields (Morais and Belwood 2019). However, high value schooling species provide a sense of overabundance and easy capture that can lead to rapid overfishing (Philipp et al. 2025; McClanahan et al. 2025). If offshore effort and catch variability continue to rise, catch uncertainty will increase and erode economic viability.

Geographic differences in oceanographic production further complicates generalizations about the compensatory fisheries potential of pelagics. While pelagic harvests are preferable to benthic species from ecological and fish trade perspectives, meeting growing demand remains challenged by knowing and implementing sustainable production limits. Therefore, generalizing about the compensatory effects of transitioning from benthic to pelagic catch needs to consider the environmental and production contexts. In general, East Africa is on the higher end of nearshore production in terms of having high light, currents, continent-associated production, and net primary productivity (McClanahan et al. 2019). Therefore, reliance on pelagic fisheries could be even more spatially heterogeneous and uncertain in less productive island and offshore tropical locations (Williams et al. 2015; Morais et al. 2023).

4.4 Recovery of Production

Fish census and modeling indicated that biomass and production recovered in studied fisheries, though initial biomass was higher in expanded areas. Recovery patterns were similar across shallow waters in both non-expanding and expanding fisheries, suggesting that reduced fishing effort, rather than spatial expansion, was the primary driver of recovery. However, recovery did not reach levels for optimal yields except at deeper reef-edge sites. Variations in recovery likely reflect differences in reef geomorphology and access to deep water, which enhances fish biomass.

Shallow areas, while productive, remain vulnerable to artisanal fishing using small boats, traps, spearguns, and nets. Without stricter nearshore access controls, passive management will result in slow biomass recovery, requiring further effort reductions to achieve optimal yields and full recovery potential. For example, a study of recovery of fish catches around a 6 km² high compliance closure found fish production increased by ~40% in adjacent fishing grounds (McClanahan 2021).

4.5 Conclusions and Recommendations

Differences in area expansion among landing sites provided an opportunity to test the potential benefits of increased offshore access (Njiru et al. 2021; Basurto et al. 2025). Results indicate that benefits were short-lived, followed by a rapid decline that persisted for 15 years after peak employment and catch. Both control and expanding sites exhibited similar outcomes, though with distinct temporal and gear-use dynamics. Expansion favored labor-intensive gears targeting smaller fish while reducing traditional gear diversity (McClanahan and Kosgei 2019). While fish biomass partially recovered, it never reached MSY, and common fisheries goals—employment, food security, income, and biodiversity—remained unmet. Instead, an ecological overshoot occurred, where stocks declined as consumer demand exceeded local production (Catton 1982).

The common-property nature of fisheries requires stakeholder agreements on restrictions for success (Vollan and Ostrom 2010). Restrictions must be agreed on and implemented successfully across governance levels. The outcomes should improve when restrictions and resource capture are informed by production potential. Catch monitoring, as described here, can guide decisions and improve acceptance of necessary adjustments. Findings from Kenya underscore the need for stronger resource protection to balance extraction activities. Maintaining resource productivity in fisheries commons will require understanding how production and

human needs are changing with social and environmental conditions (Dietz et al. 2003).

Effective restriction policies typically include limits on effort, size and species of capture, gear use, and seasonal or spatial closures (McClanahan and Abunge 2020). Evidence from Kenya shows that closures and effort reductions outperform gear restrictions for increasing catches (McClanahan 2021; McClanahan et al. 2022). However, here we see gear and effort change together and therefore the natural or uncontrolled experiment did not allow an evaluation of expansion without beach seine and associated labor increases. Future work should consider outcomes where area expansion is done in combination with gear and labor restrictions to avoid the competitive interactions reported here. It is likely that some aspects of common's governance and combinations of restrictions can achieve fisheries goals where collective governance ensures compliance (Finkbeiner et al. 2017). However, we see here how fundamental fish production and poverty threshold economics can drive most of the observed changes even after local governance has been instigated (McClanahan 2026). Understanding production relative to capture rates and human economic needs is essential for informed governance and appropriate restriction decisions. Ecological and fisheries production differ in sustaining people and ecosystems and should be central to stakeholder deliberations (McClanahan and Kosgei 2025). Minimum acceptable wages and associated effort must also be among the consideration, as they depend on balancing production potential with minimum national employment standards.

Recognizing production limits were breached in this study should prompt a policy shift from extraction to protective subsidies. Current governance expansion and subsidies have worsened unemployment and poverty by failing to support effort that meets living wage requirements (Teh et al., 2024; McClanahan, 2026). While pelagic fisheries may offer alternatives, achieving long-term sustainability and living wages remain uncertain when early expansion efforts led to a decay in fisheries services.

Achieving sustainability requires better data on production limits and gear cost-benefit trade-offs under varied management regimes. Despite conceptual simplicity, measuring sustainability faces technical, logistical, and economic challenges highlighted by long-term findings (Thiault et al., 2017; Johnson et al., 2017; Sumaila et al., 2024). To meet rising demand for healthy food (Viana et al., 2023), lost yields and nutrition must be recovered through protection of production—not expanded area access.

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Elements

Table 1. Changes or best-fit slopes in fishers/gear/day. Values presented on the log-scale from Poisson log link General Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) over annual time. Coefficient estimates are shown on the dependent variable scale, in the format slope, intercept, for each landing site and area category. The final row reports the Wald z-statistic p-values testing whether the differences in slope and intercept between expanded and non-expanded areas are statistically significant.

Landing site	Beach seine	Gillnet	Handline	Nets	Ring net	Speargun	Traps
Kuruwitu		0.009; 2.02	0.007; 0.69	0.16; 0.27		0.02; 1.75	
Tradewinds	0.0005; 2.66	0.07; 1.48	0.006; 0.69	0.09; 0.81		-0.01; 2.03	0.05; 0.28
Mvuleni		-0.006; 1.96	0.02; 1.00	-0.01; 1.74		-0.03; 2.43	-0.05; 2.33
Mwanyaza		0.03; 0.98	0.04; 1.07	0.004; 1.92		-0.06; 3.09	-0.05; 2.62
Non-expanded (Baseline)							
Slope;	0.0004;	0.03;	0.02**;	0.06;		-0.02;	-0.02;
Intercept	2.66**	1.60**	0.86**	1.18*		2.32**	1.74**
Vipingo		0.01; 1.79	0.009; 0.42	0.14; 0.57		0.06; 1.38	
Bureni		0.07; 0.56	0.002; 0.21	0.22; -0.07		-0.03; 2.26	
Kanamai		0.04; 1.24	0.008; 0.49	0.06; 0.23		0.03; 2.06	
Mtwapa	0.04; 2.33	0.07; 1.39	0.04; 1.44	0.14; 0.09	0.004; 3.49	-0.03; 2.15	0.008; 1.33
Marina	0.03; 3.44	-0.13; 4.46		-0.11; 4.11			-0.07; 1.45
Nyali	-0.004; 2.96	0.09; 0.50	0.03; 0.61	0.05; 0.21		-0.04; 2.61	0.01; 1.52
Mwaepe	-0.11; 2.21	0.04; 0.99	0.03; 1.47	0.02; 1.28	0.003; 2.54	-0.07; 3.20	-0.02; 2.33
Mgwani	0.04; 2.19	-0.01; 2.34	0.01; 0.86	0.03; 1.35		-0.06; 2.91	-0.04; 2.39
Gazi	0.01; 2.84	0.04; 1.21	0.02; 1.40	-0.01; 2.95	0.004; 3.36	-0.02; 2.03	0.007; 1.45

Expanded							
Slope;	-0.03;	-0.03*;	-0.02**;	0.04;	0.004;	0.0005;	-0.04**;
Intercept	3.27*	2.25*	1.17*	1.53*	3.13*	1.89*	1.63*
Wald test:							
Non-expanded vs.							
Expanded							
P-value							
Slope;	NS;	0.08;	0.003;	NS;		NS;	NS;
Intercept	NS	NS	NS	NS	No control	NS	NS

The double-star suffix (**) on slope or intercept values indicates the estimate is significantly different from zero ($p \leq 0.05$), while the single-star (*) indicates significance ($p \leq 0.1$).

Interpretation: For every unit increase in time (t), the log expected count increases by 0.0004 which is no different from zero. When transformed, $e^{0.0004} = 1.0004$, multiplies by 1.0004, implying we expect a slow increase of 0.04% for every unit increase in time in fishers using Beach seine for the non-expanded category.

Table 2. Changes or best-fit slopes in fishers/gear on the log-odds scale from Binomial GLMM (logit link) over annual time.

Landing site	Beach seine	Gillnet	Handline	Nets	Ring net	Speargun	Traps
Kuruwitu		-0.04; 0.13	-0.04; - 1.80	0.17; - 2.48		-0.02; - 0.39	
Tradewinds	-0.07; 0.45	0.11; -1.69	0.0006; - 2.38	0.18; - 3.41		-0.02; - 0.80	0.05; -2.81
Mvuleni		0.01; -1.26	0.07; - 2.50	0.03; - 1.68		-0.002; - 0.43	-0.04; - 0.55
Mwanyaza		0.03; -2.19	0.07; - 2.43	0.02; - 1.30		-0.07; 0.48	0.43
Non-expanded (Baseline)							
Slope;	-0.07;	0.03;	0.03;	0.10**;		-0.03;	-0.01;
Intercept	0.45	-1.26*	-2.28**	-2.23**		-0.28	-1.27**
Vipingo		-0.19; 1.33	-0.005; - 2.21	0.17; - 2.13		0.02; -0.68	
Bureni		0.06; -1.23	0.02; - 2.24	0.27; - 2.45		-0.09; 1.39	
Kanamai		0.01; -0.71	-0.02; - 1.90	0.05; - 2.42		0.02; 0.18	
Mtwapa	-0.08; 0.95	0.08; -1.26	0.03; - 1.25	0.21; - 3.59	-0.30; 4.32	-0.08; - 0.17	-0.02; - 0.93
Marina	0.04; 2.02	-0.10; 0.82		-0.08; - 0.15			-0.10; - 1.84
Nyali	-0.09; 0.81	0.14; -3.39	0.06; - 3.30	0.07; - 3.41		-0.01; - 0.99	0.04; -1.77
Mwaepe	-0.20; -0.35	0.10; -2.64	0.05; - 1.81	0.07; - 2.23	0.05; -1.17	-0.07; 0.40	-0.009; - 0.34
Mgwani	-0.06; -0.29	0.06; -1.15	0.04; - 2.76	0.10; - 2.46		-0.02; - 0.38	-0.008; - 0.55
Gazi	-0.04; -0.43	0.08; -3.09	0.03; - 2.74	0.02; - 1.07	0.07; -0.82	-0.007; - 2.04	0.02; -2.16
Expanded							
Slope;	-0.02;	-0.04;	0.006;	0.07**;	-0.06;	0.01;	-0.02;
Intercept	0.48	-0.57	-2.10*	-1.80*	0.78	-0.94*	-2.03*
Wald test:							
Non-expanded vs. Expanded							
P-value							
Slope;	NS;	NS;	NS;	NS;	No	0.09;	NS;
Intercept	NS	NS	NS	NS	control	NS	NS

The double-star suffix (**) on slope or intercept values indicates the estimate is significantly different from zero ($p \leq 0.05$), while the single-star (*) indicates significance ($p \leq 0.1$).

Table 3: Proportion of pelagic catch/to total catch per gear estimated coefficients (slope; intercept) on the log-odds scale from Binomial GLMM (logit link) over annual time.

Landing site	Beach seine	Gillnet	Handline	Nets	Ring net	Speargun	Traps
		0.002; -		0.14; -			
Kuruwitu		1.22	0.14; -3.30	2.14		0.08; -4.40	
Tradewinds	0.27; - 3.48	0.22; - 3.77	0.20; -3.72	0.08; - 1.27		0.05; -4.11	-0.08; - 1.17
Mvuleni		0.16; - 2.67	0.14; -3.51	-0.09; 2.08		0.08; -4.34	0.06; - 5.64
Mwanyaza		0.12; - 0.83	0.09; -3.28	-0.18; 2.83		0.07; -4.77	0.07; - 6.54
Non-expanded (Baseline)							
Slope;	0.27;	0.13**;	0.14**;	-0.01;	NA;	0.07*;	0.02;
Intercept	-3.48**	-2.13**	-3.46**	0.37	NA*	-4.41**	-4.48**
Vipingo		-0.004; - 2.15	0.23; -3.15	0.12; - 4.26		0.04; -3.75	
Bureni		0.12; - 3.25	0.13; -3.64	-0.20; - 1.21		0.17; -4.78	
Kanamai		-0.08; - 0.83	0.25; -4.93	-0.03; 0.55		0.20; -5.70	
Mtwapa	2.05; - 3.75	0.28; - 2.69	0.18; -3.02	0.10; 1.74	-0.21; 2.30	0.11; -5.18	-0.11; - 1.75
Marina	2.04; - 3.43	0.37; - 4.68		-0.16; 3.80			-0.06; - 4.40
Nyali	2.02; - 4.65	0.01; - 1.10	0.07; -2.86	-0.26; 5.65		0.05; -5.19	-0.04; - 5.32
Mwaepe	-1.97; - 4.66	0.12; - 1.03	0.18; -3.58	0.25; - 3.76	-0.23; 6.77	0.007; -3.25	0.28; - 5.00
Mgwani	-1.43; - 1.16	0.17; - 3.72	0.13; -5.91	0.02; 0.25		0.08; -5.70	0.25; - 8.26
Gazi	2.03; - 3.78		-0.03; - 0.40	0.05; 0.67	0.10; 0.12	-0.08; -1.69	-0.21; - 2.03
Expanded							
Slope;	-1.82**;	0.03;	0.06*;	-0.06;	-0.12;	0.07**;	-0.19**;
Intercept	-0.71	-2.11*	-2.34*	0.07	3.21*	-3.51*	-2.18*
Wald test:							
Non-expanded vs. Expanded							
P-value							
Slope;	NS;	NS;	0.09;	NS;	NA;	NS;	0.06;
Intercept	0.04	NS	NS	NS	NA	NS	NS

The double-star suffix (**) on slope or intercept values indicates the estimate is significantly different from zero ($p \leq 0.05$), while the single-star (*) indicates significance ($p \leq 0.1$).

Table 4. Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) results for predicting log fishable biomass using a Gaussian Family with identity link for the fixed effects of time, area expansion, depth, fishing, and their interactions with sites as a random factor. Estimates are on a logarithmic scale. The initial linear mixed model included two interaction terms: time × expansion and depth × expansion, alongside the main effects of time, depth, expansion, and fished(unfished), with a random intercept for site. The depth × expansion interaction was statistically insignificant ($p = 0.81$). Therefore, this term was removed in the final model. The retained time × expansion interaction was consistently significant across models ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that biomass trends over time differ between expanded and non-expanded sites. The final model explains approximately 65% of the variance in biomass using fixed effects alone, and 78% when accounting for variation between sites.

Fixed effect term	Estimate (Initial model)	p-value (Initial model)	Estimate (Final model)	p-value (Final model)
(Intercept)	0.343	NS	0.334	NS
Year (time)	0.059	<0.001	0.059	<0.001
Expansion (Expanded)	1.490	<0.001	1.50	<0.001
Depth	0.126	0.001	0.128	<0.001
Fished (Unfished)	0.862	<0.001	0.865	<0.001
Time × Expansion (Expanded)	-0.041	<0.001	-0.041	<0.001
Expansion × Depth	0.009	NS	—	—

Model fit metrics	Initial model	Final model
REML Criterion	473.6	468.6
Marginal R^2 (R^2_m)	0.64	0.65
Conditional R^2 (R^2_c)	0.78	0.78
Site-level SD (RE)	0.43	0.42
Residual SD	0.55	0.55
Observations (N)	239	239
Locations	47	47

Figures

Fig. 1. Map of the studied fishing grounds in southern Kenya distinguishing non- and expanding fishing grounds.

Fig. 2. Principal Component Axis analyses of the monthly (a) fishers/gear/day, (b) relative fishers/gear/day (Proportion of fishers per gear), and (c) pelagic/total catch ratio for the 13 studied sites based on pooled monthly gear use and catch.

Fig. 3. Butterfly plots comparing the 7 common gears in use in the expanding and non-expanding fish landing sites for (a) fishers/gear/day, (b) relative fishers/gear/day, and (c) the pelagic/total catch ratio. Significance of tests of difference presented above each gear type. Gears are organized along the x axis from most (beach seines) to least competitive (traps) in terms of smallest to largest mean body lengths. NS = not statistically significant.

Fig. 4. Times series plots of the changes in (a) total and interpolated per area effort and (b) total and interpolated per area catch (CPUA), (c) catch per unit effort (CPUE), (d) fishers per beach seine and nets, and (e) pelagic/total catch ratio for non- and expanding fishing grounds.

Fig. 5. Relationships between the intercepts and slopes of the rates of change for the 7 gears for (a) fisher/gear/day, (b) relative fisher/gear/day, and (c) pelagic/total catch ratio. Best-fit linear equations and fits shown if relationships were statistically significant.

Fig. 6. Time series plot of the estimated per area production at 2.75 and 15 meters (y1) and annual capture rates for expanding and non-expanding fishing grounds based on annually interpolated fishing areas over the 1987 to 2018 study period (y2).

Supplementary Information

Table S1. Description of Kenyan gazetted legislation relevant to small scale fisheries access and development based on 2016 legislation. These are taken from a larger set of gazetted laws for each of the two recent gazettment periods.

Category of regulation	Fisheries regulation	Source
County may develop fisheries management plans	34. (1) Each County may develop fisheries management measures and plans for fisheries resources within its jurisdiction as provided in the Fourth Schedule to the Constitution.	The Fisheries Management and Development Act, 2016
Relations between National and County governments	36. (1) Where there is any conflict between a County fisheries management plan and the management-related provisions of this Act, the Director-General shall consult with the County government and give appropriate direction.	The Fisheries Management and Development Act, 2016
Prohibited fishing gear and methods	42. (1) No person shall use, permit to be used or attempt to use or carry-on board a vessel- (a) fishing gear that has not been authorized by a valid and applicable licence issued pursuant to this Act for the purpose of fishing unless otherwise provided in this Act. (b) any fish aggregating device unless an authorization has been issued in accordance with this Act. (c) a trawl net or other net the mesh of which is less in stretched diagonal length than the prescribed mesh size. (d) the method of pair trawling for the purpose of fishing. (e) monofilament net for the purpose of fishing. (f) more than one net at a time for the purpose of fishing with trawl net. (g) attachments to any trawl net except as may be prescribed. (h) a gill net, whether drifting or set, in any river or body of water forming part of the riverine system if the mesh of the net is less than forty- five millimetres in stretched diagonal length.	The Fisheries Management and Development Act, 2016

	<p>(i) a seine nets the mesh of which is less than forty-five millimetres in stretched diagonal length.</p> <p>(j) a beach seine net for the purpose of fishing.</p> <p>(k) a seine net in any body forming part of the riverine system.</p> <p>(1) firearms or other electrical shock devices for the purpose of fishing including stunning, disabling, or killing fish or in any way rendering fish to be caught easily; or</p> <p>(m) such other gear as may be prescribed or prohibited by regulations established under this Part.</p> <p>(2) Unless otherwise prescribed, no person shall use for fishing, from an industrial fishing vessel, any net or combination of nets the mesh of which is less than —</p> <p>(a) sixty millimetres in stretched diagonal length for the meshes forming the cod-end of the net for demersal trawl nets.</p> <p>(b) forty-five millimetres in stretched diagonal length for the meshes in the cod-end for catching shrimp and other shellfish.</p> <p>(c) forty-five millimetres in stretched diagonal length for seine nets; and</p> <p>(d) in the case of a trawl net, where the sides of the net are less than the mesh of the cod-end.</p> <p>(3) No person shall use on an industrial fishing vessel a bottom trawl in coastal waters of less than fifteen meters depth.</p> <p>(4) No person shall, for the purpose of fishing, set any net across any river from bank to bank to form a barrier.</p> <p>(5) No person shall —</p> <p>(a) permit to be used, use, or attempt to use any explosive, poison, or other noxious substance for the purpose of killing, stunning, disabling or catching fish, or in any way rendering fish more easily caught; or</p> <p>(b) carry or have in possession or control any explosive, electric shock device, poison or other noxious substance in circumstances indicating an intention of using such substance for any of the purposes referred to in subparagraph (a).</p>	
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	<p>(6) Any explosive, electric shock device, poison or other noxious substance found on board any fishing vessel shall be presumed, unless the contrary is proved, to be intended for the purposes referred to in paragraph (1) (a) of subsection (42).</p> <p>(7) A person who contravenes any of the provisions of this section commits an offence and shall be liable on conviction to a fine not exceeding five million shillings or to a term of imprisonment not exceeding three years or to both in respect of industrial fishing and to a fine not exceeding one hundred thousand shillings or to imprisonment for a term not exceeding three months or to both in respect to artisanal fishing.</p>	
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Table S2. Description of nets used in the Kenyan fishery recorded during catch sampling in 35 landing sites in 5 coastal counties of Kenya. The data was collated from rapid assessment of landing sites enumerators. Additionally, numbers of fishers and material type were validated using monthly data collection.

Net type	Usage	Material type	Mesh size (inches)	Average fishers required per gear	Length (m)	Height (m)
Gillnet	Rabbitfish	Nylon	2.5	4	1100 - 1215	1.5 - 4
	Shark & Rays net	Nylon	4 - 6	5	90 - 900	14 - 40
Reefseine	Reefseine	Nylon	0.5 - 2	12	14 - 200	3 - 10
Ringnet	Dagaa	Nylon	0.25	18	70 - 150	10 - 15
	Simusimu	Nylon	0.5	22	100 - 200	21
Setnet	Setnet	Monofilament	1 - 3	3	100 - 200	3 - 5
	Setnet	Nylon	2.5 - 8	3	140 - 1500	1.5 - 4
Beachseine	Beachseine	Nylon	0.5 - 1	15	500 - 600	1.5
Trammel net	Trammel net	Nylon	3 - 5	8	50 - 100	1.5

Table S3. The number of months a gear recorded at landing site over the study period.

Landing site	Beachse ine	Handlin e	Gillnet	Ringn et	Nets	Speargu n	Traps
Kuruwitu	1	109	144	0	33	144	1
Tradewinds	78	96	167	3	125	255	160
Mvuleni	6	230	105	0	69	272	271
Mwanyaza	2	249	19	2	146	269	269
Non-expanded total, (%)	87 (2.7)	684 (21.2)	435 (13.5)	5(0.16)	373 (11.6)	940 (29.2)	701 (21.7)
Vipingo	0	56	108	0	21	90	0
Bureni	0	17	79	0	15	103	1
Kanamai	1	76	115	0	34	116	2
Mtwapa	9	165	169	7	45	154	121
Marina	201	1	10	0	11	3	131
Nyali	160	193	154	0	36	210	202
Mwaepe	12	268	107	7	112	270	258
Mgwani	31	126	182	0	120	264	261
Gazi	109	118	94	111	162	147	95
Expanded total, (%)	523 (9.2)	1020 (18.0)	1018 (18.0)	125 (2.2)	556 (9.8)	1357 (23.9)	1071 (18.9)

Table S4. Categories of commonly caught fish. List of dominant demersal and pelagic fishes recorded between 2010 – 2025. Dominant demersal represents 42 of 197 species accounting for 90% of total 16,797 individuals. Dominant pelagic represents 22 of 53 species accounting for 90% of total 1,236 individuals. Sampling was done between 2010 – 2025. Table is based on data collected at 23 landing sites sampled between 2010 and 2025. Two approaches were used in assessment 1) between 2010 and 2019 landing sites were visited a least once per quarter while post 2019 they were visited at least 3 times per month. A subset of total catch was randomly sampled and identified to genus and species. In cases where catch was small or time allowed, all the catch was measured. Total length nearest to millimetres and weight (g) of each individual fish was recorded. A total of 33,314 individuals of 298 unique species in 61 families were sampled within sampling period. Demersal species represented 62% of total sampled while 17% were pelagic or 42 and 22 species of demersal and pelagic fishes respectively accounting for 90% of individual categories.

Benthic species			Pelagic species		
Demersal species	Sample size, n	% of total	Pelagic species	Sample size, n	% of total
<i>Lethrinus lentjan</i>	2577	15.4	<i>Hemiramphus far</i>	121	11.2
<i>Lutjanus fulviflamma</i>	1642	9.8	<i>Sphyraena jello</i>	114	10.5
<i>Lethrinus mahsena</i>	1306	7.8	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	83	7.7
<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	1213	7.2	<i>Strongylura leiura</i>	72	6.6
<i>Parupeneus macronemus</i>	830	5	<i>Carangoides ferdau</i>	69	6.4
<i>Leptoscarus vaigiensis</i>	766	4.6	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i>	62	5.7
<i>Lethrinus harak</i>	766	4.6	<i>Pterocaesio chrysozona</i>	50	4.6
<i>Gerres oyena</i>	502	3	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	49	4.5
<i>Parupeneus barberinus</i>	500	3	<i>Mugil cephalus</i>	45	4.2
<i>Scolopsis bimaculata</i>	383	2.3	<i>Scomberoides tol</i>	34	3.1
<i>Aphareus furca</i>	378	2.3	<i>Euthynnus affinis</i>	32	3
<i>Lethrinus nebulosus</i>	373	2.2	<i>Caranx heberi</i>	29	2.7
<i>Parupeneus indicus</i>	312	1.9	<i>Sphyraena flavicauda</i>	29	2.7
<i>Lethrinus variegatus</i>	308	1.8	<i>Pterocaesio capricornis</i>	28	2.6
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	277	1.7	<i>Caesio xanthonota</i>	26	2.4
<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	236	1.4	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	26	2.4
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	222	1.3	<i>Megalaspis cordyla</i>	23	2.1
<i>Lethrinus olivaceus</i>	213	1.3	<i>Trachurus indicus</i>	20	1.8
<i>Lethrinus microdon</i>	188	1.1	<i>Hyporhamphus affinis</i>	18	1.7
<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	164	1	<i>Alepes djedaba</i>	15	1.4
<i>Lethrinus borbonicus</i>	163	1	<i>Carangoides gymnostethus</i>	14	1.3

<i>Lethrinus rubrioperculatus</i>	145	0.9	<i>Carangoides malabaricus</i>	13	1.2
<i>Scarus psittacus</i>	127	0.8	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	10	0.9
<i>Lethrinus sanguineus</i>	119	0.7			
<i>Lethrinus conchyliatus</i>	115	0.7			
<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	113	0.7			
<i>gnathodentex aureolineatus</i>	99	0.6			
<i>Acanthurus tennentii</i>	98	0.6			
<i>Lutjanus gibbus</i>	83	0.5			
<i>Acanthurus nigricauda</i>	79	0.5			
<i>Mulloidichthys vanicolensis</i>	77	0.5			
<i>Parupeneus heptacanthus</i>	77	0.5			
<i>Gymnocranius grandoculis</i>	76	0.5			
<i>Naso unicornis</i>	75	0.4			
<i>Chlorurus sordidus</i>	73	0.4			
<i>Acanthurus nigrofuscus</i>	68	0.4			
<i>Upeneus sulphureus</i>	65	0.4			
<i>Naso brachycentron</i>	64	0.4			
<i>Parupeneus cyclostomus</i>	62	0.4			
<i>Ctenochaetus striatus</i>	60	0.4			
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	55	0.3			
<i>Lutjanus kasmira</i>	48	0.3			

Table S5. Fishing landing sites and their classification of non- or expanded in fishing area. The initial (1995) and final area (2018) estimates (km²) are presented along with the total and annual percentage change.

Landing site name	Measurement period	Initial area, km ²	Final area, km ²	Change, %	Annual rate, %
Kuruwitu	2006-2018	1.4	1.42	1.4%	0.1%
Tradewinds	1995-2018	4.21	3.07	-27.1%	-1.2%
Mvuleni	1995-2018	2.31	2.45	6.1%	0.3%
Mwanyaza	1995-2018	2.31	2.45	6.1%	0.3%
Non-expanded sites average	1995-2018	2.56	2.35	-3.4%	-0.1%
Vipingo	2009-2018	0.75	1.49	98.7%	11.0%
Bureni	2009-2018	0.90	1.27	41.1%	4.6%
Kanamai	2008-2018	3.10	5.53	78.4%	7.8%
Mtwapa	1998-2018	2.79	4.96	77.8%	3.9%
Marina	1998-2018	2.79	4.00	43.4%	2.2%
Nyali	1999-2018	2.18	4.00	83.5%	4.4%
Mwaepe	1995-2018	2.63	4.22	60.5%	2.6%
Mgwani	1996-2018	2.20	5.40	145.5%	6.6%
Gazi	2002-2018	5.87	6.55	11.6%	0.7%
Expanded sites average	1995-2018	2.58	4.16	71.1%	4.9%
All sites	1995-2018	2.57	3.60	48.2%	3.3%

Table S6. Landing sites and the mean number of days sampled per month and per year. Averages for expanded, non-expanded, and all landing sites were calculated directly from the original dataset, not from the averages reported in the table.

Landing site	Mean number of days sampled:	
	Per month	Per year
Kuruwitu	2.6±0.2	28.5±6.2
Tradewinds	2.8±0.1	31.0±3.8
Mvuleni	2.3±0.1	26.3±2.4
Mwanyaza	3.0±0.1	33.7±5.6
Non-expanded	3.0±0.1	32.9±3.4
Vipingo	2.0±0.1	22.5±2.6
Bureni	2.7±0.2	28.1±7.7
Kanamai	2.5±0.1	26.9±5.2
Mtwapa	2.1±0.1	22.6±3.0
Marina	2.6±0.1	28.1±4.3
Nyali	3.2±0.2	36.1±4.6
Mwaepe	2.5±0.1	28.3±2.5
Mgwani	2.2±0.1	24.5±2.3
Gazi	2.8±0.1	31.7±4.0
Expanded	2.5±0.04	27.8±1.4
All landing sites	2.6±0.04	28.6±1.2

Fig. S1. Annual rates of change in (a) absolute fisher/gear/day, (b) relative fisher/gear/day and (c) pelagic/total catch ratio for the 7 common gear categories. P-values testing is for differences between non-expanding and expanding slopes. The values are from the models' findings are given in Tables 1, 2, and 3 based on the variable being modelled.